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Strain-engineered adaptive 2D photodetectors: a new approach to miniaturized reconstructive spectrometry

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Reconstructive spectrometry, straintronics, 2D materials, neural networks, miniaturized devices, micro-spectrometers.

ABSTRACT

We present adaptive, strain-engineered photodetectors based on 2D semiconductors. Our devices present a footprint of only about $40 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$, they are fabricated on transparent polypropylene substrates and integrate lithographically designed microheaters that induce controllable biaxial strain via thermal actuation, thus leading to a redshift in their spectral response. This strain-induced tunability is combined with a machine learning-based spectral reconstruction approach, where a neural network is trained on an extensive dataset of synthetic spectra and corresponding photocurrents generated from measured device responsivities under varying strain conditions. Although the system demonstrates spectral reconstruction over a relatively narrow range, it provides a compelling proof-of-concept for a miniaturized adaptive spectrometer.

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The emerging field of straintronics, i.e. the engineering of electronic properties through the application of mechanical strain, enabling dynamic control over device performance, offers a compelling route to realizing tunable optoelectronic devices.¹⁻³ By mechanically deforming a material, its electronic band structure can be modulated, leading to significant changes in both its optical and electrical behavior.⁴ This approach has attracted considerable interest for the development of adaptive photodetectors, where device performance can be continuously tuned via the application of strain.^{5,6} In essence, straintronics leverages the mechanical flexibility of materials to achieve functionalities that are unattainable by conventional static designs.

Two-dimensional (2D) materials are particularly well-suited for strain-engineered applications due to their exceptional resilience to large deformations and the high sensitivity of their electronic band structures to applied strain.⁷⁻⁹ Unlike bulk 3D semiconductors, many 2D materials can sustain substantial tensile and compressive strains without mechanical failure,^{10,11} while their bandgaps and optical absorption spectra exhibit pronounced modulations under strain. Such characteristics make 2D semiconductors ideal candidates for adaptive photodetectors, in which the active layer simultaneously serves as the sensing element and the tunable medium.

Recent advances have demonstrated that strain-tunable photodetectors can achieve significant modulation of key device parameters (including responsivity, spectral bandwidth, and response time) through controlled mechanical deformation. For instance, strain-engineered MoTe₂ photodetectors have shown enhanced responsivity in the near-infrared range,⁶ while monolayer MoS₂ devices exhibit marked increases in photoresponse under applied strain.^{5,12} Additional studies on In₂S₃ and InSe-based devices further underscore the potential of strain engineering to enhance the photocurrent

generation and to extend the operational range of photodetectors by dynamically tuning their band structures and optical properties.^{13,14}

A particularly attractive application of tunable photodetectors is in the field of spectral sensing. Reconstructive spectrometers, i.e. miniaturized devices that employ computational algorithms to reconstruct spectral information from encoded signals, offer a pathway toward compact and portable spectroscopic systems.^{15–20} By integrating adaptive photodetectors with tunable spectral responses, it becomes possible to exert real-time control over a single sensing pixel, thereby enabling on-demand spectral reconstruction at a minimum footprint.^{21–27} While the state of the art in single-pixel reconstructive spectrometry has mostly focused on fixed or electronically tuned encoding elements, the intrinsic strain tunability of the sensing pixel remains unexplored in this context.

In this work, we introduce a novel approach that integrates strain-engineered adaptive photodetectors with the concept of reconstructive spectrometry. Leveraging the high strain tolerance and sensitive band structure modulation of 2D semiconductors, we demonstrate that mechanical actuation, implemented via integrated microheaters, can dynamically tune the spectral response of a photodetector. This tunability is then harnessed to realize a miniaturized reconstructive spectrometer, thereby opening a new avenue for compact, adaptive spectral sensing systems.^{15,17} In contrast to conventional matrix-inversion techniques used in most gate-tunable van der Waals spectrometers, our system employs a neural network-based reconstruction approach, similar to the work of Darweesh et al.²⁶ A point of contrast with that work, is that we trained our neural network on a database consisting of thousands synthetic spectra and corresponding photocurrents obtained from them and the measured photocurrent responsivity of the device, rather than a limited number of experimental spectra, as explained in more detail below. This novel

training strategy enables accurate reconstruction of the incident spectrum from the strain-induced photocurrent shifts, highlighting the potential of our platform for next-generation spectroscopic applications.

We fabricated strain-engineered adaptive photodetectors on polypropylene (PP) substrates using a combination of maskless photolithography and a dry deterministic transfer technique. Prior to microfabrication, the PP substrates were planarized by heating near their melting temperature (145 °C) and applying mechanical pressure using a silicon wafer and weight assembly (see Supporting Information). We then performed maskless photolithography followed by gold deposition and lift-off to pattern the microheaters and the photodetector drain-source electrodes on top of the PP substrate (Figure 1a-b). High-quality 2D semiconductor flakes (WS_2 and WSe_2 , obtained from HQ Graphene) were mechanically exfoliated using Nitto SPV224 tape and transferred onto a Gel Film substrate (WF 4×6.0 mil, by GelPak). Flakes with the desired morphology and number of layers were identified using transmission-mode optical microscopy and differential microreflectance spectroscopy.^{28,29}

We selected flakes no wider than 20 μm at their thinnest region to be placed between the drain and source electrodes, and with a maximum thickness of seven layers to ensure a significant strain induced energy shift. However, we avoided monolayers, as this would make subsequent material transfers more challenging without damaging the previously transferred material. The chosen flakes were then transferred, using deterministic transfer technique, onto pre-patterned source-drain electrodes on the substrate.³⁰

In a final step the devices were encapsulated using a recently developed Formvar polymer technique to improve stability during thermal actuation, increase the strain transfer by about 2-fold and enhance the optoelectronic performance of the 2D material (more details in Supporting Information).³¹

Figure 1: (a) Photograph of a strain-engineered adaptive photodetector device under test. (b) Optical microscopy image of the patterned microheater actuators for local thermal expansion and the four channels, composed of drain-source pairs of electrodes, prior to the 2D material transfer. (c) Calibration curve showing the temperature (and corresponding substrate thermal expansion, assumed to be transferred as biaxial strain to the device) at MoS₂ monolayer as a function of the applied microheater current squared (mA²). By performing a linear regression fit to the data from spot 2 [blue marker position in panel (b)], we estimate a temperature variation of approximately 5.4 °C and an induced strain of about 0.07% per 10 mA² applied to the microheater actuator. The inset in panel (c) shows an optical image of one of the actuators after operation with an applied current exceeding 60 mA², indicating a safe operating limit.

Figure 1 summarizes the device architecture and strain calibration. Panels (a) and (b) present optical images of a representative device. In panel (a), a homebuilt probe card with gold-coated copper contacts is pressed onto the terminals of the microfabricated circuit on the PP substrate, making electrical contact with the selected device electrodes. The entire setup is enclosed in an electrically grounded Faraday box and maintained under a vacuum of approximately 5×10^{-6} mbar.

In Panel (b), two microheater actuators are visible, with four contact channels in the middle defining positions where distinct transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) can be placed. The microheaters locally heat the polymer substrate, and as a result of its thermal expansion, an in-plane biaxial strain can be induced in the transferred 2D

samples.^{32,33} Further details on the fabrication and performance of the microheater actuators are provided in Ref.³³

In panel (c), the calibration curve (see Supporting Information for the details on the calibration) demonstrates the dependence of the local temperature (and corresponding strain) on the applied microheater current squared (mA^2) for two channel positions, marked in orange (spot 1) and blue (spot 2) in panel (b). The data was obtained by monitoring the exciton shift in MoS_2 in these two spots upon microheater biasing and comparing it with the response obtained upon heating the whole device with a macroscopic heater. The temperature change at both spots remains approximately the same due to the device configuration used, where two microheater actuators are positioned on opposite sides.

The device enables fast response, up to 8 Hz,³³ and control on local temperature variations of up to 30 °C, inducing reversible biaxial strain of approximately 0.4%, which relates to spectral redshifts of up to 20 nm. To ensure device stability, multiple devices were tested to determine a safe operating limit of 60 mA^2 for the microheater bias, beyond which irreversible damage (melting of the surrounding PP) may occur, as illustrated in the optical image of the inset in Panel (c). Within this range, the microheater circuit maintains resistivity variations below 3%, enabling controlled and reproducible strain modulation by adjusting only the circuit current, as the Joule heating power is proportional to the square of the applied current (see Supporting Information Figure S2).

Figure 2: (a) Close-up optical microscopy image of a fabricated photodetector, illustrating the device architecture including the 2D semiconductors bridging the source–drain electrodes and the adjacent microheater. (b) Current vs. time measured on the WS_2 channel 2 (unbiased heaters) while the device is illuminated with different wavelengths to extract its spectral response. For each wavelength the illumination is switched ON and OFF, allowing to directly measure the photocurrent, and then the wavelength is varied for the next ON/OFF cycle. (c) Photocurrent spectra response for both WS_2 (blue) and WSe_2 (orange) recorded under four different microheater bias conditions, showing the spectral shift of the excitonic peak as a function of induced strain in the 2D material.

Figure 2 details the optoelectronic performance of the strain-tunable photodetector. Panel (a) provides a close-up microscopy image of a typical device, showing 2D semiconductor flakes bridging the source–drain electrodes close to the nearby microheater. This configuration ensures efficient strain transfer and supports on-chip integration. We initially transferred four distinct TMDCs flakes onto the four channels aiming to use distinct materials with their A exciton features spanning a broad range of the spectrum. However, the MoS_2 and $MoSe_2$ flakes (channels 1 and 4) exhibited insufficient signal-to-noise ratio and lacked temporal stability after the transfer process (see Supporting Information Figure S5). As a result, they were excluded from this study. In this particular device, only the WS_2 and WSe_2 samples (channels 2 and 3) remained functional after fabrication. Therefore, the micro-spectrometer footprint can be estimated as $40 \times 20 \mu m^2$, corresponding to the active area of the WS_2 and WSe_2 samples.

The dynamic response of the photodetector was evaluated by recording the current at a fixed bias voltage between drain and source electrodes as a function of time while the device is illuminated with different wavelengths. The currents reading were made one by one, selectively applying bias only to the electrodes associated with the channel being actively measured, while keeping all other channels electrically floating. As depicted in Figure 2b, the time-resolved current obtained during incident monochromatic light [full width at half maximum (FWHM) ~ 8 nm] ON/OFF cycles reveals a fast and reproducible switching behavior, illustrating the stability and high signal-to-noise performance of the device. The current with light ON is subtracted from the one with light OFF to calculate the photocurrent for each incident light wavelength from 400 nm to 800 nm, with steps of 5 nm. The device's spectral response for each channel and strain induced is then recorded.

In Figure 2c, the photocurrent spectra response measured at different microheater bias levels are presented for two channels: WS₂ and WSe₂. The data illustrates a clear spectral shift: with increasing strain, the excitonic peak in the photocurrent response systematically shifts, confirming that thermal actuation effectively modulates the band structure of the 2D semiconductors. This tunability of the spectral response is a crucial feature for the adaptive functionality of the photodetectors.

Figure 3: Schematic reconstruction process. Spectral responsivity D is experimentally characterized as a function of both wavelength and strain state [see Figure 2(c)]. Using this information, it is possible to predict the resulting photocurrents when the device is exposed to an arbitrary spectrum. We exploit this to build a training database consisting of pairs of synthetic spectra and their predicted photocurrent response, which we use to train the reconstruction neural network to reconstruct the incident light spectrum.

Building on the strain-tunable photodetector platform, we further explored its application in reconstructive spectral sensing. Rather than employing conventional matrix inversion techniques used in many gate-tunable van der Waals heterostructure spectrometers, our approach exploits the strain-induced spectral shifts to encode spectral information. To achieve spectral reconstruction, we developed a neural network framework trained on an extensive synthetic dataset. Figure 3 schematically illustrates the process of device calibration, AI model training, and performance evaluation. Each device channel is based on a distinct 2D material. For each channel, the spectral response is experimentally recorded under different strain conditions as induced by specific

microheater biases, thereby establishing the device calibration, as demonstrated in Figure 2c for two channels and four strain levels.

Since acquiring a large experimental dataset of different incident test spectra for all channels across the full range of strain conditions was impractical, we generated synthetic spectra and corresponding photocurrent responses for AI model training. For each synthetic spectrum, a matching set of photocurrent values was computed by integrating the spectrum with the calibrated spectral response of all channels at different strain levels, effectively simulating the expected device outputs for a broad range of input spectra. A total of 30,000 synthetic photocurrent sets, each paired with its corresponding synthetic spectrum, was used to train the neural network model, together with an additional 10,000 for validation and a further 10,000 for testing. Details on the generation of synthetic spectra and the neural network architecture used can be found in the Materials and Methods section and will be published in more detail elsewhere.

In practice, an unknown incident spectrum generates a set of photocurrent values across n channels for each strain level S . This results in a dataset of $n \times S$ photocurrent values, which serves as input for the AI model to reconstruct the original spectrum. A key parameter in this process is the spectral discretization, which defines how the spectrum is divided into discrete intervals for accurate reconstruction. This approach allows for tuning the reconstruction resolution as a function of the model's training time and complexity.

Figure 4: Testing the device with two channels (WS_2 and WSe_2) and four strain levels. In panel (a), synthetic generated spectra (long-dashed curves) and its reconstructed spectra (short-dashed curves). In panel (b) and (c), reconstructed spectra (short-dashed curves) made by the neural network applied to real photocurrent measurements, compared to the incident light spectra acquired with a commercial spectrometer (solid curves).

Figure 4 illustrates the proof-of-concept for the proposed reconstructive microspectrometer. The device, also shown in Figure 2, operates with only two channels, WS_2 and WSe_2 . The spectral response calibration was performed for four strain levels, induced by applying 0 mA^2 ($\sim 0\%$ strain), 17 mA^2 ($\sim 0.12\%$ strain), 34 mA^2 ($\sim 0.24\%$ strain) and 51 mA^2 ($\sim 0.36\%$ strain) to the microheater, resulting in a spectral shift of 16 nm (20 nm) for WS_2 (WSe_2) within their respective A exciton spectral ranges.

After training, the neural network model successfully reconstructed synthetic spectra with high accuracy, as shown in Figure 4a. For real incident spectra—monochromatic peaks with $\sim 8 \text{ nm}$ FWHM centered at 550 nm, 600 nm, 650 nm, 700 nm and 750 nm—the model was able to reconstruct single peaks that are closely spectrally aligned with the actual ones. As expected, spectra in the regions of the A excitons of the employed 2D materials (~ 630 and $\sim 750 \text{ nm}$ respectively) were reconstructed more accurately than those outside that spectral region. It is noteworthy that the peak at 550 nm (green) has a somewhat shifted reconstruction and also shows an artifact secondary peak at 750 nm. The quality of reconstruction in different spectral regions depends on the information content available in the device's responsivity, which, as can be appreciated in Figure 2c,

is not homogeneous throughout the whole spectral range. Additionally, in future work, we plan to explore training strategies for the neural network that incorporate a penalty for the output reconstructed spectra. This could help suppress artifacts and nonphysical features, leading to cleaner and more reliable spectral outputs.

Although only two channels and four strain levels were used, the results convincingly demonstrate that strain-induced tuning can serve as an effective mechanism for encoding spectral information in miniaturized spectrometers. In another test-of-concept, shown in the Supporting Information Figure S7, only one material (WS_2) in one channel under six strain levels could be used for spectral reconstruction in the A exciton range vicinity.

While the current implementation achieves spectral reconstruction over a limited wavelength range—corresponding to the extent of the excitonic shift—this proof-of-concept lays the foundation for further advancements. A promising avenue for future work is the integration of additional 2D semiconductor channels with complementary bandgaps. For instance, employing multiple TMDCs across different electrodes could effectively broaden the spectral encoding range and improve reconstruction resolution and accuracy. Such a multi-channel approach would allow each material's intrinsic spectral response to cover distinct segments of the spectrum, thereby enabling a more comprehensive and higher-resolution spectral analysis. Additionally, using a monochromatic light source with narrower FWHM peaks than those employed in this study, along with a finer energy step calibration, could further enhance the resolution of the proposed miniaturized spectrometer.

In summary, we have demonstrated a novel strain-engineered photodetector platform that leverages the unique mechanical and electronic properties of 2D semiconductors for adaptive spectral sensing. Integrated microheaters enable precise thermal actuation, inducing strain that modulates the band structure and shifts the spectral response of the

devices. By harnessing these strain-induced shifts, we developed a reconstructive micro-spectrometer, with a footprint of only $40 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$, using a neural network trained on data derived from combining synthetic spectra and the experimental photocurrent spectral response of each device's channel and strain induced level. Although the current implementation reconstructs spectra over a limited range, our results provide a compelling proof-of-concept for miniaturized, adaptive spectroscopic systems. Future work will focus on further enhancing the spectral range and resolution through improved device architecture and integration of multiple 2D material channels, paving the way for next-generation compact spectral sensors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials. Four different two-dimensional (2D) semiconducting materials were employed in this study: molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) sourced from a natural mineral (Molly Hill Mine, Canada), tungsten disulfide (WS_2), tungsten diselenide (WSe_2), and molybdenum diselenide (MoSe_2) obtained from HQ Graphene. The substrate used for device fabrication was $500 \mu\text{m}$ thick PP (PP30-FM-000340, Goodfellow Cambridge Limited).

Optoelectronic Characterization. The optoelectronic performance of the devices was characterized in a custom-built vacuum electrically grounded chamber equipped with a homebuilt probe card. The incident light shined the sample through a borosilicate window in the chamber. All measurements were performed under vacuum conditions of approximately 5×10^{-6} mbar, after maintaining the system under vacuum for at least 24 hours. An initial calibration measurement applying all strains levels, used to allow the device to stabilize, is performed but not considered in the final analysis. Subsequent calibration and testing steps are then carried out on the settled device. The incident light

power density ranged from $11 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ to $38 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$. To ensure consistency across the spectral range, the measured photocurrents for the device's calibration were normalized to a constant incident power, considering the linear photocurrent response with light intensity up to hundreds of mW/cm^2 for this device architecture.³¹

A wavelength-adjustable light source (Bentham TLS120Xe) was used to calibrate the spectral response of the photodetectors over the wavelength range of interest. This light source produces peaks with an approximate FWHM of $\sim 8 \text{ nm}$, and its intensity varies with wavelength. Therefore, the measured photocurrent response as a function of wavelength was corrected to account for a constant-intensity light source.

Photocurrent measurements were carried out using a Keithley 2450 source measure unit, which provided both voltage biasing and current readout functions during the characterization experiments. Different drain–source voltages (V_{SD}) were applied depending on the specific sample, with values chosen based on current–voltage (I – V) curve analysis to optimize both signal-to-noise and signal-to-background ratios. For the device shown in Figures 2 and 4, a V_{DS} of 0.1 V was applied to both the WS_2 and WSe_2 sample channels.

AI model training. Randomly generated synthetic spectra were obtained as follows. We considered spectra with a random number of peaks ranging between 1 and 3. For a given spectrum, once the number of peaks had been selected, peak positions were chosen from a uniform distribution spanning the spectral range (400 to 800 nm, in this case), and likewise, full widths at half maximum were also chosen for each peak, ranging between 5 and 50 nm. The shape of each peak was equally chosen randomly from three alternative possibilities, namely a Lorentzian, a Gaussian or a Voigt shape. Lastly, once a random spectrum had been generated in this way, we discarded it if the intensity at either of the limits of the spectral range was greater than 5% of the maximum intensity within the

range. If a synthetic spectrum was deemed acceptable, the photocurrents it would produce were calculated by multiplying it by each of the measured photocurrent response curves of WS₂ and WSe₂ [see Figure 2(c)], followed by integration over the spectral range, as indicated in the upper central panel of Figure 3.

For the neural network we adopted a multi-layer perceptron design, with an input layer of size equal to the number of detector channels multiplied by the number of strain levels (8, in this case). The input layer was followed by a number of deep layers with a variable number of neurons per layer, interspersed by a non-linear activation (we used the ELU activation function). In actual practice we used four deep layers with 41 neurons per layer; although we did not perform a systematic optimization of these hyper-parameters, we did check that varying them around these default values resulted in no appreciable change. The number of neurons in the final output layer determines the spectral resolution; in this work we imposed a spectral resolution of 5 nm, which required 81 neurons in the output layer. So as to enforce the normalization of the resulting spectrum, a SoftMax layer was used. The model was implemented using Pytorch³⁴, and relied on the scikit-fda Python package³⁵.

Formvar polymer encapsulation. To enhance device stability and thermal-induced strain actuation, a recently developed Formvar encapsulation technique was applied following device fabrication and samples transfer.³¹ This encapsulation step plays a critical role in preserving the mechanical integrity of the 2D materials during thermal cycling. Moreover, it increases the strain gauge factor by approximately 2-fold, resulting in significantly larger excitonic peak energy shifts under the same temperature variation applied to the PP substrate. It has also been reported that Formvar encapsulation increases the maximum achievable strain from approximately 1.4% to 2.3%, and devices fabricated on PP substrates demonstrate enhanced optoelectronic performance when encapsulated

with Formvar, including higher and faster photocurrent response as well as improved device longevity. For the encapsulation step, 50 μl of Formvar solution ($\sim 1\%$ w/w polyvinyl formal in 1,2-dichloroethane, Formvar solution from Merck company) was spin-coated (3000 rpm and 40 s) using an Ossila spin coater onto the device surface and left to dry for 24 hours under ambient conditions (22 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 45% RH).

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information: Details on device fabrication, 2D flake exfoliation and transfer, and the Formvar polymer encapsulation method. Analysis of the number of layers for the flakes used in the device shown in Figure 2, determined via differential microreflectance spectroscopy. Complete calibration data for the microheater actuator, including: (i) study of the safe current limit for the dual microheater actuator, (ii) differential microreflectance analysis of a large monolayer flake covering the entire active area, and (iii) photoluminescence (PL) mapping of the same flake confirming temperature homogeneity across the device. Test of the device with only one channel (WS_2) under six strain levels, leading to spectral reconstruction in the A exciton range vicinity.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The manuscript was written with contributions from all authors, who have approved the final version. T.L.V. conceived and fabricated the adaptative spectrometer device with conceptual input from A.C.G. and T.P. Sample transfers and device preparations were performed by T.L.V. in collaboration with S.N.V. and S.P. Device calibration and experimental tests were carried out by T.L.V. and T.P. All experimental data analysis was conducted by T.L.V. The neural network model was developed and performed by E.R.H. with conceptual input from T.L.V. and A.C.G. The manuscript was written by T.L.V., A.C.G., and E.R.H., with contributions from C.M. The project was supervised by A.C.G. and C.M.

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